

GEOGRAPHICAL AND DEMOGRAPHIC IN CENSUS CENSUS THE PLACE OF INDICATORS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6596336>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th May 2022

Accepted: 14th May 2022

Online: 30th May 2022

KEY WORDS

population, population list, human potential, economy, demography, statistics, ethnic composition, religious composition, births, deaths, settlements.

ABSTRACT

This article covers the historical aspects of the census as well as its scientific basis. There is scientific information about the population lists obtained in the territory of Uzbekistan. The list of the population planned to be carried out in the Republic on the basis of the state program is stated.

Modern economy development basic from the source one - is the human potential of the country. For efficient use of human resources of the population location, content, natural reproduction indicators, education level, economic activity and similar demographic data will be required. About the population all complete information directly population list transfer through collected.

Population lists - country or certain in the region known time or demographic, economic and social data of the population living in the period process package. Population censuses are based on scientific requirements and practical needs answer, collect information on population, composition and location in order to is carried out.

main purpose of the census is to obtain reliable and objective information on the state of the population and the dynamics of development in the Republic of Uzbekistan, necessary for the definition and implementation of priorities of state policy in the field of socio-economic and socio-political development.

main tasks of the census :

- Expand the database to assess changes in the population and demographic situation in the country in order to improve the health of the population , improve the living conditions of women and children, develop measures to support families ;
- long, medium and short-term forecasts and programs for socio-economic development of cities and other settlements, placement and use of labor resources ;

- implementation of current calculations, calculations and forecasts of the number and composition of the population in the period between censuses;

- conducting research on socio-economic development .

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • last name, first name, patronymic; • date and place of birth; • age; • jeans; • millati; • Citizenship; • place of residence (location); • knowledge of languages; • marital status; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of children; • household structure; • housing conditions; • employment; • sources of funding for living; • migration (internal and external). • information;
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There are a number of scientific principles for conducting censuses. Their in total event and events cover get principle eng importantCoverage of the total population in a given area at the time of the census condition Demographics (gender, age, marital status), economic characteristics (occupation, field or type of economic activity), education (literacy, to school go), ethnic symptoms (nation, language, sometimes religion) and etc. data is obtained. These data can be compared over time and region valid to be for, total to the population a kind of content questions provided that is, censuses across the country are based on a single program must be carried out. It is based on the recommendations of the UN . Population The relevant information is taken from each person personally to ensure accuracy. The list goes on at a time when people are living in their place, mostly in the winterIn the short term, held for several days or weeks, but not all data at a critical (serious) moment (usually the first day of registration) is taken, so far the dead and

born is not displayed. Answers list leaflets unique written in a copy.

Population list population soni and composition about information known a date. On registration for fulfillment of the condition date and time clear to be displayed need This time of the list critical moment is called. From ancient times the population was calculated in different ways. Greece , Babylon (Mesopotamia), Egypt , Rome , China and In Japan population is known from historical sources. They are mainly fiscal (taxation) and military goals intended without held, usually only men, that is persons who have the opportunity to participate in military operations and pay taxes covering

Jami The list of population and composition was first published in 1790. was held in the United States in In 1801, Great Britain, France, Denmark and Held in Norway. In the middle of the XIX century in European countries special statistics organizations barpo made population lists quality was an important factor in the

transfer. In 1870-79, 48 countries in the world, 54 in 1880-89, 57 in 1890-99, the first ten of the XX century The census was conducted in 74 countries. Population lists of the twentieth century initially covered 64 percent of the world's total population. From World War II then the census became even more widespread. Population censuses 1945-54 in 168 countries, and in 1969-74 in 179 countries. Current at the time population lists of the world almost all countries is being held.

The country in the study of the state of demographic processes in the country The census data conducted in the territory play an important role reaches According to sources, in Uzbekistan in 1897, 1926, 1939, 1959, 1970, 1979, 1989 years population list conducted. Uzbekistan in the territory first The census was conducted in 1897, and this census Data on the number of families, population, population in Uzbekistan at the end of the XIX century age and jeans, ethnic composition, such as birth, death demographic about processes imagination yield to do help gave 1897 in 3730 ming person lived 4460 thousand in 1926, 8261 thousand in 1959, 11799 thousand in 1970, 1979 in 15391 mingni formed reached

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 11, 2020 No. 710 "Uzbekistan In the Republic In 2023 population to the list to take Resolution "On measures for preparation and conduct" done. Ministers Of the Court to this decision application so that "Uzbekistan Preparation for the population census in the Republic in 2023 and its transfer order about 9 chapter, 73 banddan consists of Nizom confirmed.

According to the resolution, the population census in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023 1 - 25 November, State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the floor Cadastre agency 2022 June 1st until population to the list get for

necessary which was amount cartographic materials (city and village population points schematic plans and maps) with provide setting given.

According to the general provisions of the Charter, registration is November 1-25, 2023 days and the exact time of registration start is November 1, 2023 hour 00.00 reaching determined. To the list get transfer duration 25 kunniforms. To register when collecting respondents' personal information the demographic circumstances that occurred after the date of acquisition are not taken into account. 2023- year From November 1st then born children for to the list get documents not replenished, but replenished for those who died after that date. In this case, the information about the deceased is his adult, treated based on available information from eligible family members or the neighborhood office filled in. Administrative-territorial units boundaries account take population points living population sonini shown without population points complete list structure provide function Karakalpakstan Republic Ministers Council, provinces and Tashkent city, districts (cities) authorities defined. Registrar by staff prepared assembly lists results based on city and villages (this including men and Women) on first information city and village to the population separated formed without. Republic of Uzbekistan, Republic of Karakalpakstan, provinces, Tashkent city,

tuman and cities on population to the list preliminary data of the acquisition will be prepared by March 1, 2024. Population to the list get results chop reach Committee and his regional authorities by December 1, 2025 in official print media, as well as

electronic sources, users wide ommasi for ommabop in publications, (brochures, press releases, atlases, presentation materials and in others), Of the Committee official on the website will be announced by posting.

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